

ON THE STUDY OF THE USE OF CALCIUM OXALATE
MONOHYDRATE IN THE INVESTIGATION OF RARE
EARTH AND THORIUM ACTIVITIES

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It has been shown that $\text{CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is a faithful carrier of rare-earth and thorium activities. The distribution of activities under the experimental conditions has all along been found uniform. Calcium is therefore a good non-isotopic diluent for the study of thorium and rare-earth activities as oxalates. The fact that calcium oxalate carries cent per cent rare-earth and UX_1 activity, has been utilised to prepare carrier-free UX_1 from aged uranyl nitrate solution with about cent per cent recovery. It can be claimed to be a very convenient method for determining counter geometry factor. It has been shown that calcium can be estimated within a very short time with aged uranyl nitrate solution where UX_1 acts as a radioactive indicator. In time of measurements, the soft β^- 's from UX_1 are cut off and the hard β^- 's from UX_2 in equilibrium are actually counted. This is very convenient, because changes due to resultant effect of absorption and scattering over a wide range of source weight are negligibly small. So no correction factor is required. It has been shown that rare earths can be uprooted from uranium, thorium, zirconium, beryllium and aluminium to the desired level by calcium oxalate ($\text{CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) as scavenger. In this work the ratio of rare earths to uranium etc. elements (mentioned above) has been brought to about 1:10⁶. It has been found to be a very simple laboratory process of decontamination.

There is no simplified method for the determination of rare-earth and UX_1 activities by isotopic dilution. Previously the rare-earth and thorium activities in question were diluted by lanthanum and thorium respectively and precipitated as oxalate, and this was ignited to oxide which was then transferred to counting tray for activity measurements in the solid way. In case of rare earths, it is time consuming and is handicapped by other factors, well known to workers in the field. Besides the difficulties mentioned, the activities from the thorium series also play a disturbing role in case of weak activities. In view of these difficulties American investigators (Coryell and Sugarman, "Radiochemical Studies: The Fission Product", Book-3, 1951, p. 1681) tried to find out a condition to treat rare-earth and thorium oxalates as primary standards. But the conditions they found out were not also very convenient and faithful in the studies lasting for a few days with solid samples. Difficulties with thorium, as mentioned with special reference to radioactive contaminants, remain unanswered. One of the objectives of our investigation is to find out a non-isotopic diluent which yields a faithful primary standard and at the same time which can carry all the thorium and rare-earth activities along with it and that the conditions can be made such that a uniform distribution is achieved through the entire mass of the precipitate so as to enable a fraction to be used as in the usual practice of isotopic dilution.

It has further been observed that various methods have been described in the literature (Crookes, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1900, 66, 409; Booth, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1951, 28, 144; Erbacher, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1944, 252, 282; Aten and Barendregt, *Physica*, 1950, 16, 760; Wahl and Bonner, "Radioactivity Applied to Chemistry", 1951, p. 431) for the

separation of UX_1 in equilibrium with U_1 . No simple method has thus far been successful to separate cent per cent UX_1 containing no carrier ion in it. The second objective of this investigation is to find out a non-isotopic carrier which carries UX_1 from U_1 , but the objective UX_1 ion and the carrier in question can be easily separated from each other. In this type of separation procedure, the carrier for UX_1 should be chosen such that it should carry the ultramicro quantity of thorium (UX_1) leaving the bulk of U_1 behind it and at the same time it is better if the carrier in question should not have a tendency of complex formation so that any simple chemical or physico-chemical procedure can be applied without much complexity for uprooting a few atoms of thorium (UX_1), leaving behind the bulk of carrier employed. Selection naturally comes to calcium because of the following advantages: (a) Calcium has got very little tendency to form complex ion. (b) Oxalates and fluorides of calcium are insoluble in acetic acid and it has been found by us that calcium oxalate in acetic acid medium carries about cent per cent thorium, and the conditions may be made such that calcium oxalate may be perfectly freed from uranium too. In the present investigation calcium oxalate has been used as a carrier of UX_1 and a method of separating UX_1 freed from any carrier has been described.

It has been further observed that for various types of nuclear studies, decontamination of trace of rare earths from elements like uranium, thorium, zirconium, aluminium and beryllium is indispensable. It also forms a part of the study whether trace of rare-earth oxalates can be carried along with calcium oxalate, leaving behind the elements in question as double oxalates. Although various methods of decontamination have been described in the literature of nuclear science, such a simple procedure as studied by us has been found to be very suitable for simple laboratory work. With these objects in view, a study on the use of calcium oxalate monohydrate was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents used were all of Analar quality. A stock solution of uranyl nitrate in nitric acid was prepared. It was filtered through sintered glass crucible and allowed to remain as such for about six months before quantitative investigation started. Carrier-free Pm^{147} and Y^{91} , which were used in the present investigation, were supplied by Harwell, England, as chloride in hydrochloric acid solution.

Role of Calcium Oxalate Monohydrate in the Determination of Rare-earth and Thorium (UX_1) Activities.—To test the suitability of the use of calcium as a good isotopic diluent for thorium and rare earths, unknown calcium was determined by using UX_1 , Pm^{147} and Y^{91} . The procedure consists in coprecipitating the thorium and rare-earth activities along with $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$. The latter was precipitated in acetic acid medium by the addition of oxalic acid. It was observed that some calcium remained in the solution. This difficulty was later overcome by precipitating calcium from 50% alcoholic solution. The description of a typical experiment is given below.

A known amount of the active solution is taken to which is added a known amount of $CaCl_2$ solution. Free mineral acid is neutralised with ammonia using methyl red as indicator and then acidified with acetic acid. The solution is next diluted to about 65 c.c. and heated to boiling. To the hot solution are added 75 c.c. of absolute alcohol

and 10 c.c. of oxalic acid (containing about 1g. of $C_2H_2O_4 \cdot 2H_2O$) all at once with constant stirring. This is allowed to stand for sometime when the precipitate readily settles. The precipitate is washed by centrifugation, slurried with acetone, transferred to a nickel tray and dried under an infra-red lamp, taking care that the temperature does not exceed 105° . The precipitate on the tray is weighed as $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ and counted in the usual way. Unknown calcium is then determined by comparing with a known standard.

TABLE I

Estimation of calcium using UX_1 , Pm^{147} and Y^{91} as indicating nuclei.

Indicating nuclide.	Amount of calcium taken.	Amount of calcium found.	Indicating nuclide.	Amount of calcium taken.	Amount of calcium found.	Indicating nuclide.	Amount of calcium taken.	Amount of calcium found.
Pm^{147}	22.7 mg.	23.1 ± 0.6 mg.	Pm^{147}	46.5 mg.	46.5 ± 0.9 mg.	Y^{91}	28.4 mg.	29.0 ± 0.6 mg.
Pm^{147}	19.9	19.9 ± 0.5	UX_1	22.7	22.6 ± 1.3	Y^{91}	34.1	33.9 ± 0.7
Pm^{147}	23.3	23.6 ± 0.4	UX_1	26.1	26.8 ± 1.5	Y^{91}	39.8	39.7 ± 0.9
Pm^{147}	34.9	34.8 ± 0.7	UX_1	19.3	19.0 ± 1.0	Y^{91}	45.4	46.1 ± 1.1
			Y^{91}	11.4	11.4 ± 0.2			

Direct Use of Aged Uranyl Nitrate Solution in the Determination of Calcium by Isotopic Dilution.—In our previous operations we separated UX_1 from aged uranyl nitrate solution. It has also been observed by us that aged uranyl nitrate solution as such can conveniently be used as a source of UX_1 in the determination of calcium by the principle of isotopic dilution. A known amount of an aged uranyl nitrate solution was added to the solution of the unknown calcium and precipitation of $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ was done in the way as already described. The precipitate was washed through centrifugation and a fraction of the precipitate was taken for counting. Unknown calcium can thus be easily estimated. Results are indicated in Table II.

TABLE II*

Estimation of calcium using aged uranyl nitrate solution itself as a source of UX_1 .

Ca taken (mg.) ...	11.4	14.2	17.0	22.7	28.4	36.9
Ca found (mg.) ...	11.2 ± 0.4	13.9 ± 0.4	16.5 ± 0.6	22.9 ± 0.8	27.8 ± 0.8	37.3 ± 1.0

*Uranium taken in each case = 0.13371 g. Volume of operation = 150 c.c.

$CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ as an Intermediary for the Preparation of Carrier-free UX_1 .—As the separation of calcium and thorium can be easily achieved, $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ can suitably be employed for the preparation of carrier-free UX_1 in quantitative yield (vide Table III). Our present method consists of the following three simple steps:

1. Carrying of UX_1 in equilibrium with U_1 with $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$.
2. Isolation of UX_1 from calcium through $Fe(OH)_3$ scavenger.
3. Separation of iron by continuous extraction with (isopropyl) ether. The aqueous layer which is obtained consists of cent per cent UX_1 in hydrochloric acid, free from any carrier. That the recovery is cent per cent has been studied by the following procedure.

The solution of uranyl salt after uprooting UX_1 with $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ was tested for the completeness of separation by precipitating a fresh quantity of $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$. No appreciable activity was detected, indicating that carrying of UX_1 by $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ was cent per cent. The procedure was followed in all the steps mentioned above. We also tested the activity carried in the following way to have a duplicate check. Standard sample was prepared from known amounts of uranium and calcium. This was treated as a standard for comparison with the carrier-free product. In case of the same amount of uranium, identical activity within statistical error was always observed, both from liquid samples and solid samples as $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$. This evidently proves that $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ is a faithful carrier and the procedure adopted is perfectly reliable. Further evidence to the findings mentioned above and suitability of our procedure for measuring counter geometry was given by evaporating an aliquot portion of the solution of carrier-free UX_1 on a thin mica foil and counting through a delimiting diaphragm (Cook and Duncan, "Modern Radiochemical Practice", 1952, p. 267). After making necessary corrections, the observed number of counts was found to agree well with that calculated theoretically within the limits of statistical accuracy (Table III).

TABLE III*

Testing the recovery of carrier-free UX_1 and the suitability of the method for determining counter geometry.

No.	Counting from solid samples.		Counting from liquid samples.		Counting through delimiting diaphragm.	
	No. of counts per min. recorded from		No. of counts per min. recorded from		No. of disintegrations per min.	
	Standard. †	Final recovery product.	Standard. †	Final recovery product.	Theoretical	Exptl.
1.	4590	4645	3006	3002	329600	339800
	± 122	± 145	± 49	± 49		± 13060
2.	4590	4380	3006	2910	329600	339800
	± 122	± 123	± 49	± 49		± 10370

* Both the experiments were started from 0.4457 g. of uranium to prepare carrier-free UX_1 .

† Standard samples were prepared as described in the experimental portion.

Role of $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ in the Decontamination of Rare-earths from Materials commonly used in Atomic research such as U, Th, Zr, Be, Al, etc.—In order to study whether calcium oxalate by repeated precipitation could uproot rare earths from the materials mentioned above, these were converted into double oxalate by excess of ammonium oxalate to which were added 0.247 mg. of lanthanum and a known amount of Pm^{147} as a rare-earth indicator. Successive calcium oxalate precipitations were then made. Results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV†

Use of CaC₂O₄.H₂O in decontaminating rare earths from Be, Al, Zr, Th and U.

Major constituent (M).	Initial ratio.	M : R in soln. after precipitation with CaC ₂ O ₄ .H ₂ O.		
	M : R.	1st. pptn.	2nd. pptn.	*3rd. pptn.
Be	1 : 2.47 × 10 ⁻³	1 : 1.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	1 : 1.8 × 10 ⁻⁷	1 : 8.6 × 10 ⁻⁹
Al	1 : 2.47 × 10 ⁻³	1 : 8.8 × 10 ⁻⁶	1 : 5.2 × 10 ⁻⁷	1 : 2.6 × 10 ⁻⁸
Zr	1 : 2.47 × 10 ⁻³	1 : 8.1 × 10 ⁻⁶	1 : 5.3 × 10 ⁻⁷	1 : 3.3 × 10 ⁻⁸
Th	1 : 2.47 × 10 ⁻³	1 : 2.6 × 10 ⁻⁵	1 : 1.2 × 10 ⁻⁶	1 : 4.4 × 10 ⁻⁸
U	1 : 2.47 × 10 ⁻³	1 : 1.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	1 : 5.3 × 10 ⁻⁷	1 : 2.1 × 10 ⁻⁸

† M stands for the major constituent such as Be, Al, Zr, Th and U; R stands for rare earth. Initial concentration of M in all cases is about 100 mg. and that of R is 0.247 mg. of lanthanum per 100 c.c. of the solution. 104 mg. of CaC₂O₄.H₂O was precipitated in each case.

* Rare-earth activity was carried here with lanthanum oxalate except in the case of thorium where it was carried with thorium oxalate itself.

DISCUSSION

The method to use calcium as a non-isotopic diluent for the measurement of rare-earth and thorium activities by precipitating as calcium oxalate is free from the troubles already mentioned. That CaC₂O₄.H₂O spreads well and furnishes very reliable results is evident from our studies on the determination of calcium using UX₁ (thorium isotope), Pm¹⁴⁷ (representative of the rare earths), Y⁹¹ (a representative of the chemical analogue of the heavy rare earths). The method can be claimed very reliable and free from complexities. When from the tracer scale we go to increase the rare earth or thorium content, the method, as is usual, does not succeed, presumably because of the complex oxalato-ion formation. It has been observed by us that the maximum inactive carriers, which we can have in all these cases, are about 0.5 mg. each of yttrium, thorium and lanthanum (in case of Pm). When we go beyond this limit of 0.5 mg. carrier per 150 c.c. of the solution, error creeps in due to incomplete carrying. This limitation does not, however, stand in our way in distribution and other radiochemical studies with tracer amount of thorium and rare-earth activities. Besides, use of calcium is very convenient when we deal with long lived rare-earth activities which are costly to procure, because when the study is over we can easily separate the active constituent once again by the easy chemical procedure. It should further be stated that in the case of UX₁, the soft β⁻'s from the isotope in question were cut off by 35.3 mg./cm² of aluminium absorber. So we measured the hard β⁻'s from the short-lived UX₂ in equilibrium with its mother. It is well known that absorption and scattering correction in case of hard β⁻'s for a source weight is very negligible over a wide range of source weights (Coryell and Sugarman, "Radiochemical Studies: the Fission Products," Book-1, 1951, p. 56) for comparative studies, and in this respect it is a very convenient isotope where correction in the estimation by isotopic dilution

is not required (vide Fig. 1). In this respect UX_1 or Y^{91} can conveniently be used even in the estimation of calcium by isotopic dilution in simple cases. It should be

FIG. 1

mentioned that in the case of Cu^{64} we meet with soft β^- 's where changes in self-absorption and self-scattering against changes in source weight are very predominant and some error is prone to follow. It should further be stated that in our measurements we have estimated different quantities of unknown calcium, keeping rather the activity the same, which is evidently the same as measuring the differing quantities of unknown activities. It is also an evidence that the distribution of the activities over the $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ is very uniform over a wide range. Any fraction of the $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ taken, as is usually done, is a measure of the total activity. The cause of this uniform distribution of thorium and rare-earth activities over $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ is a subject matter of further study.

The fact that unknown calcium can conveniently be estimated by using a known amount of aged uranyl nitrate solution as a source of UX_1 (vide Table II) is much easier than the classical method in consideration of the simplicity and the time of operation. Even the amount of uranium used up can be used again as soon as the amount of UX_1 sufficiently grows up.

It must be pointed out that carrying of cent per cent UX_1 or rare-earth activities by $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ offers a very great advantage. We have utilised it, besides the purpose mentioned above, to have carrier-free UX_1 in solution so that by dropping an aliquot portion on a thin mica foil we can determine the counter geometry. The procedure followed by us is not, however, very simple. There are other ways wherein it is possible to recover cent per cent UX_1 directly from calcium and that will form the subject matter of a separate study.

In our study of decontaminating rare earths from elements such as beryllium, aluminium, zirconium, uranium and thorium, the solution left after three successive calcium oxalate precipitations was acidified with hydrochloric acid and any trace of

rare-earth activities was tested by carrying as lanthanum oxalate, whilst the final degree of decontamination achieved in case of thorium was tested by precipitating thorium oxalate itself. The results showing the degree of decontamination achieved in different stages are shown in Table IV. Simplicity of operation allures one to adopt it to uproot rare earths in day-to-day laboratory work. Even in case of analysis dealing with small traces of rare earths, calcium oxalate can serve as a good scavenging agent.

From the facts stated above it can be claimed that calcium oxalate monohydrate is a very useful carrier for rare-earth and thorium activities in the field of study already mentioned. Other uses of this reagent will form the subject matter of further study.

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